

Research Paper

Influence of simulated spatial conditions and reverberation on speech intelligibility prediction accuracy with the Simulation Framework for Auditory Discrimination Experiments (FADE)

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ABSTRACT

Considering complex acoustic scenes in rehabilitative audiology and hearing device assessments requires understanding the influence of multiple interacting factors. Speech intelligibility models provide a systematic way to explore and predict these effects. However, they must be able to deal with acoustic conditions including different numbers and spatial configurations of sound sources, and the presence of reverberation. Here, the binaural implementation of the automatic speech recognition-based approach Simulation Framework for Auditory Discrimination Experiments (FADE) was validated for predicting speech intelligibility in ten acoustic scenes of varying spatial complexity without and with reverberation. The outcomes were compared with data from normal-hearing listeners and with the predictions of an index-based, intrusive model, the Binaural Speech Intelligibility Model (BSIM). The interferer constellation in anechoic conditions had a large effect on speech recognition thresholds, which was predicted with a high accuracy by both models ($0.90 \leq R^2 \leq 0.97$ between modeled and predicted data). This spatial influence was greatly reduced in reverberant conditions, which was correctly predicted by the models. Reverberation had a detrimental effect on speech intelligibility, with larger changes in measured than in predicted data. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that FADE is able to predict the influence of interferer constellation for normal-hearing listeners even in complex conditions and performs comparably to the well-established BSIM, without the need to separate speech and noise inputs or a reference. However, FADE needs improvement to correctly predict the detrimental effect of reverberation on speech intelligibility.

1. Introduction

In hearing research, evaluating speech intelligibility across a wide range of acoustic conditions is essential for understanding how various factors such as noise source location and reverberation contribute to speech intelligibility (i.e., the property of the speech signal to be understandable) and human speech recognition (i.e., the property of the human to be able to understand speech).¹ Traditionally, clinical assessments focus on relatively simple listening scenarios, which do not fully reflect the complexity of real-world environments. However, everyday listening often involves multiple competing sound sources and

reverberant spaces highlighting the need for speech intelligibility and speech recognition assessment methods that can handle greater ecological validity. One promising approach to meet this need is the use of speech intelligibility models, which offers a systematic, efficient and reproducible way to assess speech intelligibility across various conditions (Kollmeier and Kiessling, 2018). For these models to be effective, they must accurately predict human speech recognition performance in environments of varying complexity. This capability would enable researchers to efficiently explore and compare human speech recognition in different configurations, thereby reducing the reliance on time-consuming listener tests. Ultimately, the development of robust,

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¹ We refer to “speech intelligibility models” and “speech intelligibility” throughout the manuscript whenever the property of a certain (speech) signal is referred to. However the terms “automatic speech recognition” (ASR) and “human speech recognition” (HSR) are widely spread in the literature to describe the property of a system or an individual listener (with whom we obtain “speech recognition thresholds” to assess speech intelligibility of the signals employed).

accurate models paves the way toward model-based auditory diagnostics and individualized hearing aid fitting, enhancing clinical outcomes and patient care.

The current study focuses on evaluating the binaural extension of the Simulation Framework for Auditory Discrimination Experiments (FADE) (Kollmeier et al., 2016; Schädler et al., 2020b, 2016) in the context of speech intelligibility in binaural listening conditions with a focus on realistic sound source positions including multiple masker sources, in either anechoic or reverberant environments. The model's predictions are compared to both empirical speech recognition data from normal-hearing listeners and to predictions from the Binaural Speech Intelligibility Model (BSIM, Beutelmann et al., 2010) which serves as a well-established reference for speech intelligibility modelling under binaural conditions.

FADE combines an auditory inspired front-end with a classifier-based decision stage that uses a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) in combination with a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM). These statistical models operate on internal auditory representations to estimate speech intelligibility based on the discriminability of spectro-temporal feature patterns over time. Rather than relying on explicit knowledge of the target and masker signals, FADE learns to distinguish between different possible alternatives of detected speech signals by modeling the statistical structure of auditory cues derived from simulated listening conditions. In this sense, it is considered data-driven, as it infers intelligibility from learned internal patterns, rather than predefined acoustic metrics. A key feature of FADE is that it provides reference-free predictions of speech recognition thresholds (SRTs), meaning it estimates SRTs directly without the need for an external mapping function from model outcomes to measured data. The SRT refers to the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at which 50 % of the speech is recognized correctly. Furthermore, FADE's architecture is well-suited for modeling aided listening conditions, which involve nonlinear signal processing such as compression and noise reduction, commonly used in hearing aids (Schädler et al., 2020a, 2018). Since FADE relies on an internal representation of speech in noise rather than on raw acoustic signals, it can naturally incorporate these nonlinear transformations within its processing chain. In addition, FADE supports the individualization of hearing loss by adapting its front-end to reflect listener-specific auditory characteristics. This includes both threshold-related aspects, such as elevated pure-tone thresholds across frequencies, and suprathreshold deficits, such as a reduced spectro-temporal or intensity resolution. These factors are crucial for accurately modeling speech perception in hearing-impaired individuals. Schädler et al. (2020a) demonstrated that combining threshold and suprathreshold individualization resulted in the highest prediction accuracy of speech recognition performance by intelligibility for hearing-impaired listeners across various noise conditions. These developments underline FADE's strong potential for individualized audiological predictions, particularly for applications such as hearing aid fitting and the prediction of speech intelligibility in listeners with a given hearing impairment. However, to extend the model's applicability to ecologically valid, spatial listening scenarios, a fully evaluated binaural version of the model is required.

While Schädler et al. (2018) introduced a better-ear version of FADE, their study primarily focused on evaluating speech intelligibility predictions from a binaural noise suppression scheme, and did not include a systematic investigation of the binaural processing itself within the FADE model. Building on this, Schädler et al. (2020b) proposed a more comprehensive binaural extension of the better-ear approach, incorporating both better-ear listening and contralateral inhibition to more closely approximate human binaural processing. This version was evaluated in the context of anechoic speech intelligibility and only considered a single noise source presented at varying azimuths. The present study builds upon these developments by conducting a systematic evaluation and comparison of both the better-ear only and better-ear combined with contralateral inhibition FADE approaches under a wide range of realistic spatial configurations that mimic a setup

of a typical living room. These include listening conditions with multiple spatially distributed noise sources and the presence or absence of reverberation, designed to better represent everyday listening scenarios. By extending the validation of the model to these more realistic conditions, this study takes a critical step toward the application of FADE in individualized audiological modeling in ecologically valid listening scenarios.

To comprehensively assess the model's performance, its predictions are compared both to those of BSIM, a widely used analytical model for binaural speech intelligibility, but also to empirical speech intelligibility data collected specifically for this study. While previous work, such as Beutelmann et al. (2010), primarily examined scenarios with a single noise source whose spatial position was systematically varied, these conditions do not fully capture the complexity of everyday listening environments. The new data, gathered from normal-hearing listeners, provides a carefully controlled yet more realistic benchmark, reflecting spatial configurations and sound source orientations based on a living room setting. A living room is a common and relevant environment for hearing aid users (Mansour et al., 2021), who spend around 60 % of their time in relatively quiet environments (Humes et al., 2018). Given that the living room often represents such typical acoustic conditions, it serves as an appropriate context for examining speech intelligibility and evaluating model predictions under ecologically valid scenarios.

In contrast to FADE, BSIM follows an analytical approach, relying on explicit calculations of SNRs after binaural processing stages such as interaural suppression and better-ear selection. BSIM computes an intelligibility index, derived from an internal version of the Speech Intelligibility Index (SII) (ANSI, 1997), which must then be mapped to predicted SRTs using empirical reference functions. While BSIM has been validated extensively and performs well in structured scenarios, it depends on access to clean target and masker signals and assumes monotonous relationships between index values and intelligibility outcomes.

While BSIM provides a well-established analytical framework for predicting binaural speech intelligibility, it represents only one approach within a broader landscape of speech intelligibility models. Numerous other models are available, each offering unique strengths and applications. They differ in their front-end processing, which simulates peripheral auditory mechanisms like cochlear filtering, and in their back-end prediction methods, which involves higher-level processing stages mapping the internal representations to perceptual outcomes like speech intelligibility. Front-ends may be physiologically or psychoacoustically motivated (Biberger and Ewert, 2017; Holube and Kollmeier, 1996; Jørgensen et al., 2013; Kates and Arehart, 2014; Staller et al., 2007) or based on effective modeling (e.g., Beutelmann et al., 2010; Taal et al., 2011). Back-ends may rely on static measures such as SNR (ANSI, 1997), temporal measures (Steeneken and Houtgast, 1980), fixed optimal detectors (Holube and Kollmeier, 1996; Jørgensen et al., 2013; Jürgens and Brand, 2009), or generalized optimal detectors (Schädler et al., 2016). Binaural stages can involve better-ear listening, i. e. taking into account the ear with the higher SNR due to the head shadow, or binaural interaction between both ears, such as the equalization-cancellation (EC) principle (Durlach, 1963), used in the BSIM (Beutelmann et al., 2010). An approach based on computing binaural masking level differences was used in the model for predicting binaural speech intelligibility developed by Lavandier and colleagues (Lavandier et al., 2012, 2010a, 2010b). A detailed overview and comparison of many speech intelligibility models in terms of their suitability for predictions in hearing-impaired listeners, with hearing aid processing, and under binaural conditions can be found in Schädler et al. (2018, Table 1). Most existing models are limited either by their dependence on signal separation (e.g., requiring isolated speech and noise inputs), by their constrained applicability to simplified spatial scenes, or by limited flexibility in handling more advanced binaural mechanisms within a unified framework. To address these limitations, the present study evaluates the binaural extension of the FADE model, a data-driven

speech intelligibility model based on a generalized optimal detector, in acoustic scenes of varying spatial complexity, both with and without reverberation. This positions FADE as a potentially flexible and scalable tool for advancing predictive modeling in hearing science and, in the long term, for supporting model-based rehabilitative audiology.

In recent years, several Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)-based approaches have been proposed for speech intelligibility predictions. ASR-based approaches offer the advantage that they can make predictions without an empirical reference and without access to the clean speech or noise signals, enabling direct estimation of speech intelligibility. This feature is particularly important for aided speech intelligibility predictions, i.e. for evaluating hearing devices. Similar to FADE, Fontan et al. (2020) developed an ASR-based model approach using HMM and GMM. They reported high correlations between model predictions and measured data, including data of older, hearing-impaired listeners. However, the results also show a large spread between empirical and simulated outcomes, as indicated by large root-mean-square errors (RMSEs). Furthermore, their study design was limited to monaural speech intelligibility in quiet using different types of speech material. Another ASR-based approach was proposed by Karbasi et al. (2020), who combined an ASR-based system with various signal-based measures of speech intelligibility. Their non-intrusive approach was able to accurately predict the speech intelligibility of hearing-impaired listeners in different noise scenarios. Similarly, Roßbach et al. (2022) introduced an ASR-based deep learning network model functioning as a phoneme classifier. Their model achieved high prediction accuracy for hearing-impaired listeners across different types of maskers. However, all the ASR-based models described above focused exclusively on monaural listening conditions and are therefore not suitable for predicting speech intelligibility in realistic binaural settings, such as reverberant rooms. In contrast, FADE was developed to extend ASR-based modeling into the binaural domain (Schädler et al., 2020b, 2018). Recent developments in ASR-based modeling have started to address binaural processing by incorporating mechanisms like the equalization-cancellation strategy (Huelsmeier et al., 2021; Rennies et al., 2022) or by combining phoneme posteriorgrams from both ears (Roßbach et al., 2025).

Several studies have evaluated models for speech intelligibility predictions in various rooms in terms of the SRT. Beutelmann et al. (2010) assessed BSIM across different spatial configurations of speech and noise in an anechoic room, a listening room, a classroom, and a church with short distances between the speech source and the listener, so late reverberation did not affect the speech signal. For normal-hearing listeners, correlations of 0.80–0.93 were found between measurements and model predictions. Rennies et al. (2011) extended BSIM to a version differentiating between useful (early) and detrimental (late) reverberation to improve the prediction performance in reverberant conditions. Ahrens et al. (2019) examined measured and predicted speech intelligibility in real and simulated environments, varying the spatial configuration, reverberation and masker type. The study found that the binaural speech intelligibility model by Jelfs et al. (2011) could predict relative differences in speech intelligibility between different reproduction methods after calibration to each spatial configuration using measured median results in a reference room. However, the model by Jelfs et al. (2011) was not able to predict speech intelligibility in situations where target and masker were co-located, i.e. where they were convolved with the same impulse response, as it analyzes only differences in the impulse responses of target and masker signal. Huelsmeier et al., 2021 found that the performance of models applying a blind binaural front-end version of BSIM (Hauth et al., 2020) or the contralateral inhibition approach of FADE (Schädler et al., 2020b) led to a comparable accuracy as the reference model (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006) in an anechoic condition, an office, and a cafeteria. Schädler (2022) investigated speech intelligibility predictions with FADE in a simulated living room environment with a varying number of maskers, different head rotations, and a grid of target positions for listeners with

normal and (aided) impaired hearing. While the study offers a valuable theoretical framework and visualization of predicted effects, it lacks empirical validation. No comparison with measured listener data was provided to evaluate the accuracy of the predictions. Furthermore, the binaural aspects of the model were simplified, as only a better-ear approach was used to represent spatial hearing. Importantly, the acoustic scene used in the study was still under development and included sounds with unresolved licensing issues, which prevented public release and thus hinders reproducibility and independent evaluation of the model's performance.

Taken together, it is still open how ASR-based speech intelligibility models perform for binaural and spatially complex scenes in comparison to conventional approaches like BSIM. Therefore, the current study addresses the following research questions: 1) How do the binaural approaches implemented in FADE using i) automatic better-ear listening only and ii) automatic better-ear listening combined with contralateral inhibition perform in predicting speech intelligibility under various simulated acoustic conditions in a realistic scene, and how do they compare to the binaural approach of BSIM? 2) Can FADE accurately predict SRTs in a simulated reverberant condition as a proof of concept?

Predictions were conducted for different spatial configurations in anechoic and reverberant conditions, evaluating both better-ear and binaural processing versions of FADE against BSIM and data obtained from normal-hearing listeners.

2. Methods

2.1. Virtual acoustic environment

The study was conducted using an audio-visual model for virtual reality of a real living room lab (Schütze et al., 2021). The room had dimensions of 4.97 m x 3.78 m x 2.71 m (length x width x height) and a volume of 50.91 m³. Next to the simulated living room was a kitchen room with the dimensions 4.97 m x 2.00 m x 2.71 m (length x width x height) and a volume of 26.94 m³. Both rooms were connected through a door. The living room included a range of windows on one wall, and walls made of plasterboard and brickwork. In front of the row of windows were a couch, two armchairs and a couch table. The couch was oriented towards a TV on a TV board. Furthermore, there were a bookshelf, a cabinet and curtains. Using a simulated room in contrast to measured impulse responses offers the possibility of changing parameters in a systematic way.

The room simulation was implemented in TASCAR (Grimm et al., 2019). The latest version of TASCAR including a documentation is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13984298>. The living room and kitchen were modeled as two separate TASCAR scenes, because the room model did not allow coupled rooms. The acoustic scene present in the kitchen was recorded in TASCAR and then included in the living room as a source positioned at the connecting door between both rooms, similar to the procedure reported by Fichna et al. (2023) (see below for more details). Reflection and damping coefficients of the surfaces within the room models were optimized with frequency-dependent absorption coefficients of the respective surface materials. Early reflections were simulated with a first order image source model. Late reverberation was generated by applying a simple feedback delay model based on the work by Schroeder (1961) and Rocchesso and Smith (1997). Here, the audio is initially encoded in a first order Ambisonics sound field, and subsequently, a varying amount of rotation is applied at every reflection to create a diffuse sound field. The parameters gain, absorption and damping coefficients, and reverberation time T_{60} belonging to the definition of late reverberation in TASCAR are optimized to match frequency-dependent T_{60} values provided by Schütze et al. (2021). This was done using an optimization tool included in TASCAR. This tool optimizes the required parameters based on the direct-to-reverberant ratio (DRR) and T_{60} in the frequency bands 0.25–0.5 kHz, 0.5–1 kHz, 1–2 kHz, and 2–4 kHz using a grid search and an optimization for the

minimum error. Within the TASCAR DRR optimization tool, the international speech test signal (Holube et al., 2010) served as a test signal to compute the DRR of the scene.

2.2. Sound sources and receiver

Different locations of the sound sources and the position of the receiver used in this study are illustrated in Fig. 1. The room size, source and receiver positions, and acoustical parameters reflect the typical living room described by Schütze et al. (2021). A receiver R was positioned at the coordinates $[x = 2.95, y = 3.30, z = 1.10]$ m relative to the bottom left corner of the room. It was simulated by a parameterized head-related transfer function (HRTF) receiver (Schwark et al., 2022) in TASCAR. This receiver uses a variant of the Spherical Head Model (Brown and Duda, 1998) with additional shadow effect and reflection filters as introduced by Ewert et al. (2021).

Omnidirectional sound sources were positioned at the coordinates shown in Table 1, based on coordinates defined by Schütze et al. (2021). These positions have been chosen to reflect typical positions of a TV, furniture and, by that, location of sitting persons, in a typical living room (Laudenbach, n.d.; Mörrixbauer et al., 2019).

2.3. Stimulus definition and condition generation

The individual noise sources LR, K and TV were optionally turned on or off in different combinations. For each noise condition, a recording of the acoustic environment with the corresponding active noise sources was acquired using the TASCAR toolbox. The sound sources were selected to create variations in speech intelligibility while also reflecting their typical spatial positions in everyday life.

The masker was a stationary noise with the long-term spectrum of a male speaker, denoted as “male stationary noise” in the following. This masker was generated from the INoise signal (Holube et al., 2008) transformed to a male frequency spectrum (Schubotz et al., 2016). This way, the spectrum of the masker is similar to the spectrum of the male target speaker, which will be introduced later.

The noise sources LR and TV were calibrated in TASCAR to a root-mean-square (RMS) level of 65 dB SPL at the source position, and K

Table 1

Coordinates of sound sources and receiver in the virtual living room and kitchen in x, y, and z direction in m, and root-mean-square sound levels of noise sources in dB SPL. The positions are measured from the bottom left corner of the living room.

Room	Source / Receiver	x / m	y / m	z / m	Level / dB SPL
Living room	Receiver (R)	2.95	0.75	1.05	–
Living room	Television (TV)	2.95	3.30	1.10	65
Living room	Living room left (LL)	1.83	1.88	1.02	adaptive level
Living room	Living room right (LR)	4.08	1.88	1.02	65
Living room	Kitchen door (K)	0.94	3.83	0.98	64
Kitchen	Kitchen corner (KC)	4.68	3.97	1.10	53
Kitchen	Kitchen right (KR)	2.92	5.02	1.10	65
Kitchen	Kitchen left (KL)	1.78	5.02	1.10	65

was calibrated to 64 dB SPL at the source position. The sound pressure level of noise source K corresponds to the RMS level at the same position in the acoustic model of the neighboring kitchen room in TASCAR. At the position of the door in the acoustic model of the kitchen, a virtual sound recording was performed using TASCAR, and the resulting RMS level was calculated. Three noise sources were active in the kitchen: a dishwasher at position KC with a noise level of 53 dB SPL, two persons at positions KL and KR, each speaking at a level of 65 dB SPL. These three sources also played back male stationary noise. The sound level of sources KL and KR corresponds to an average conversation level, and the level of KC was estimated based on average dishwasher sound pressure levels (Chen, 2020; Flowers, 2015).

Speech stimuli were generated by rendering binaural room impulse responses (BRIRs) between the target position LL and the receiver position R. The head was rotated towards position LL. The generated BRIRs were convolved with sentences of the German matrix sentence test (Oldenburger Satztest) OLSA spoken by a male speaker (Kollmeier et al., 2015; Wagener et al., 1999). This test consists of lists of 20 sentences, where each sentence follows the same structure of 5 words (name, verb, numeral, adjective, object). The sentences are semantically unpredictable, and for each word category, 10 options exist.

All stimuli, including noise conditions and target talker BRIRs, were rendered in an anechoic and a reverberant version of the living room in order to assess the influence of reverberation. The tested noise conditions were the following: 1) TV only, 2) LR only, 3) K only, 4) TV and K, and 5) TV, LR and K. In the following, the conditions are denoted as 1) TV, 2) LR, 3) K, 4) TV-K, and 5) TV-LR-K, respectively. All five conditions were presented without reverberation (denoted by suffix “_anechoic”) and with reverberation (denoted by suffix “_reverberant”). The first part of each condition name (before the suffix) indicates the names of active noise sources, and the last part indicates the presence of reverberation. The RMS noise levels measured at the receiver position are shown in Table 2 for anechoic and reverberant conditions. The rendered BRIRs and noise stimuli are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15096923>.

Table 2

Root-mean-square sound levels of different noise conditions in dB SPL for the anechoic and reverberant conditions, measured at the receiver position R.

Condition	Anechoic level / dB SPL	Reverberant level / dB SPL
TV	57.2	66.7
LR	61.3	67.6
K	43.9	55.0
TV-K	57.4	67.1
TV-LR-K	62.4	70.6

Fig. 1. Overview of a virtual living room simulation with room dimensions and positions of receiver R, target (LL) and noise sources (LR, TV, K, KL, KR and KC, respectively (cf. Table 1)). The upper room is the kitchen, the lower room is the living room.

2.4. Room acoustic parameters

To acoustically characterize the used virtual acoustic environment, different room acoustic parameters were calculated. Reverberation time (T30), speech clarity (C50) and interaural cross correlation (IACC) were determined from BRIRs rendered between listener position *R* and source position *LL* with the listener's head orientation towards the source. T30 and C50 were calculated for the left and right channel separately. The calculations were performed using the ITA toolbox (Berzborn et al., 2017).

2.5. Listeners

Fourteen native German listeners participated in the study, i.e., seven female and seven male persons at the age of 18 to 28 years (mean age: 25.0 ± 2.7 years). All listeners reported no hearing problem, had mean pure-tone hearing thresholds of the frequencies 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz below 20 dB HL and were therefore defined as normal hearing (World Health Organization, 1991). The listeners were paid for participating in the study.

2.6. Speech intelligibility measurements

The measurements were conducted in a soundproof room with acoustic panels on the walls and ceiling, and carpet on the floor. The experimenter was sitting in the same room to guide the experiments. Stimuli were played back via free-field equalized Sennheiser HDA 200 headphones (ISO389-8:2004) connected to a Ferrofish Pulse 16 AD/DA converter. The playback was controlled via a computer with a Windows system and the software Oldenburg Measurement Applications (OMA). The OMA software has been calibrated using a Brüel & Kjær Artificial Ear Type 4153 with a Brüel & Kjær $\frac{1}{2}$ " Pressure Capsule Type 4132, connected to a Brüel & Kjær Measuring Amplifier Type 2610 and a Brüel & Kjær $\frac{1}{2}$ " Preamplifier Type 2669.

At the beginning of the measurement appointment, the listeners were informed about the study and gave written consent approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg. Pure-tone hearing thresholds were then measured to confirm that the listeners were normal-hearing. After that, the SRT measurements were conducted.

SRTs of the participants were measured with German matrix test lists, each consisting of 20 sentences. For SRT measurements with a closed set response format, i.e., where the listeners were provided with a list of all 50 words present in the test, participants were equipped with a screen and a mouse. For an open set response format, i.e., where the matrix words were not visible, the experimenter used the screen and mouse to process the participants' oral feedback. In the beginning, two training sessions were conducted. This involved one session with a closed set response format of the German matrix test, and one session with an open set response format. After this training, the measurement conditions were presented in a randomized order and with an open set response format. The noise level was kept constant for each condition, and the speech level was adjusted adaptively to meet a intelligibility rate of 50 % using the procedure of Brand and Kollmeier (2002). The noise level was set based on the level measured at the receiver in the TASCAR toolbox, so the noise level varied across conditions.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Measured SRTs were statistically analyzed using the software IBM SPSS Statistics. First, a 2-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the factors SPATIAL CONFIGURATION and REVERBERATION was conducted. Due to a significant interaction between the factors INTERFERER CONSTELLATION and REVERBERATION, additional 1-way repeated measures ANOVA analyses with post-hoc tests were carried out. To test the factor INTERFERER CONSTELLATION, two

separate 1-way repeated measures ANOVA were carried out, one for anechoic data and another one for reverberant data. The factor REVERBERATION was tested by comparing the anechoic and reverberant data for each interferer constellation with a *t*-test for dependent samples. The ANOVA analyses were carried out with a Bonferroni correction to correct for multiple comparisons.

To compare the correlation coefficients of the different models and, by that, test whether one model has a significantly higher correlation with the measured data than another model, a *t*-statistic for dependent samples was applied. The null hypothesis of this test is that both tested models provide the same correlation with the measured data. According to Chen & Popovich (2002), this *t*-statistic was computed as

$$t = (r_{13} - r_{23}) \sqrt{\frac{(N-3)(1+r_{12})}{2(1-r_{13}^2 - r_{12}^2 - r_{23}^2 + 2r_{13}r_{12}r_{23})}} \quad (1)$$

where r_{12} is the correlation between model A and model B, r_{13} is the correlation between model A and measured data, r_{23} is the correlation between model B and measured data, and N is the sample size. The resulting *t*-statistic was then compared to the *t*-distribution with $N-3$ degrees of freedom using the cumulative distribution function, and the 2-tailed *p*-value was reported to show whether the difference between the compared models is significant.

2.8. Speech intelligibility predictions

SRTs were predicted using two different models. The first model was FADE (Schädler et al., 2020b; Schädler et al., 2016). This model uses an automatic speech recognizer to simulate the outcomes of speech intelligibility and psychoacoustic experiments. As inputs, FADE requires speech and noise signals in the time domain, which are mixed at different SNRs. From the mixed, i.e., noisy signals, logarithmically scaled Mel spectrograms are computed, which resemble the human perception of frequencies. At this stage, the individual hearing abilities of the modeled listener are simulated by defining attenuation and distortion components according to Plomp (1978).

The attenuation component is implemented by replacing every level variability below the frequency-dependent hearing threshold by the hearing threshold. Here, a profile of a normal-hearing listener with assumed frequency-independent hearing thresholds of 0 dB HL was used. In addition to simulating listeners' hearing thresholds, FADE also simulates a supra-threshold distortion component D by multiplicative Gaussian noise. In this study, a distortion of 1.9 dB was applied, according to an approximation proposed by Hülsmeier et al. (2022). They estimated D from the pure tone average (PTA) across the frequencies 0.5, 1, 2 and 4 kHz:

$$D = 1.9\text{dB} + 0.08 \cdot \text{PTA} \quad (2)$$

Following this equation, the distortion of 1.9 dB is the result for a PTA of 0 dB HL, which was assumed for the simulated normal-hearing listener.

As a next step, separable Gabor filter bank (SGBFB) features (Schädler and Kollmeier, 2015) are extracted for the left and right channel of the logarithmically scaled Mel spectrograms. These features then serve as an input for an automatic speech recognizer consisting of an HMM and a GMM. The recognizer was trained and tested with the same noisy speech signals at different SNR values (i.e. matched training). Since the test material components are known from the training, FADE is interpreted as a generalization of the optimum detector approach for speech intelligibility (Holube and Kollmeier, 1996; Jürgens and Brand, 2009) representing the performance of the best listeners. The model then determines the SNR at which 50 % of the words are identified correctly, i.e. the SRT. More details about the procedure can be found in Schädler et al. (2016).

FADE was used in two different binaural versions, which differ in the feature extraction stage, and the performance of both versions was

systematically compared. The first version applied a model of automatic better-ear listening (*ABEL*) by concatenating the feature vectors of the left and right channel, thereby allowing the system to implicitly select the more informative ear. The second version extended this approach by incorporating a combination of better-ear listening with binaural processing based on contralateral inhibition (*CAIN*) (Schädler et al., 2020b). In this version, the feature vectors from the left and right channels were concatenated along with an additional vector representing the difference between the two channels, capturing the interaural interaction. Contralateral inhibition is a biologically inspired mechanism in which the signal information from one ear (side) is used to suppress or reduce the corresponding signal in the opposite ear. This process may help to unmask relevant speech information that may be masked by competing noise, particularly when the masker is dominant on one side. It thereby effectively enhances the SNR, which leads to improved speech intelligibility. Unlike *FADE ABEL*, which relies solely on monaural cues, *FADE CAIN* includes this interaural difference vector as an additional feature, explicitly modeling binaural interactions as additional features.

The second model was *BSIM* by Beutelmann et al. (2010) combining an EC stage (Durlach, 1963) in each frequency band with the SII (ANSI, 1997). *BSIM* requires separate input signals of speech and noise for the left and right ear, so there are four input signals in total. The individual hearing thresholds are applied by adding uncorrelated masking noise to the input noise. Here, hearing thresholds of 0 dB HL were applied for all frequencies. A gammatone filterbank (Hohmann, 2002) in the range of 146 to 8346 Hz is used to filter the input signals, resulting in a signal representation similar to that on the human basilar membrane. An EC process (Durlach, 1963) is then applied in each frequency band, independently. This process estimates binaural unmasking by compensating ITDs and ILDs. First, the ITD is estimated for each frequency band, separately for speech and noise. Then, an attenuation factor is computed (equalization stage), which leads to an SNR maximization in the cancellation step. In this cancellation step, the left ear signal is subtracted from the right ear signal and a maximum SNR is achieved. The binaural SNR is calculated from the outputs of the EC stage and compared to the monaural SNRs from the left and right ear, respectively. The maximum SNR is selected. Using the SII, this maximum SNR is mapped to an index value between 0 and 1. For this index, a high number encodes a high speech intelligibility, and vice versa. To map the resulting SII to an SRT, a reference SII of 0.2 according to Beutelmann et al. (2010) and Wagener et al. (1999) was applied in this study. This reference SII of 0.2 corresponds to an SRT of -7.1 dB SNR for a monaural presentation of the German matrix test in test-specific stationary noise. Therefore, the *BSIM* can be considered as reference-based.

BSIM was applied in two different binaural modes. The first mode was the original model version using a combination of better ear listening and binaural processing. Here, the EC stage was switched on (denoted “*BSIM EC on*” in the following), so in addition to better ear listening, an SNR maximization based on the EC processing was performed. In the second mode, the EC stage was switched off, resulting in better ear listening only (denoted “*BSIM EC off*” in the following).

3. Results

3.1. Room acoustic parameters

Reverberation time T30, speech clarity C50, and interaural cross correlation IACC were calculated for the simulated room using the ITA toolbox (Berzborn et al., 2017).

Table 3 shows frequency-dependent room acoustic parameters of the simulated living room. The parameters are based on a rendered BRIR using TASCAR. For the BRIR, the source was located at target position *LL* and the receiver was at listener position *R*. The receiver, modeled by a parameterized HRTF (Schwark et al., 2022), was rotated towards target *LL*. Using a parameterized HRTF does not convey the exact same spatial

Table 3

Frequency-dependent room acoustic parameters in the simulated room for a source at target position *LL* and a receiver at position *R*, directed towards *LL*. The reverberation time T30 in s and speech clarity C50 in dB are shown for the left and right channel of the receiver, and interaural cross correlation IACC is shown as the modulus.

Frequency / kHz	T30 / s (left)	T30 / s (right)	C50 / dB (left)	C50 / dB (right)	IACC / modulus
0.125	0.50	0.50	9.9	5.6	0.91
0.25	0.55	0.55	11.9	5.1	0.48
0.5	0.52	0.52	13.1	7.3	0.33
1	0.53	0.53	10.2	10.7	0.63
2	0.49	0.49	11.4	8.9	0.53
4	0.37	0.37	15.6	13.4	0.42
8	0.20	0.20	25.6	23.9	0.27

perception as if listeners would listen to the room with their own ears, but it allows the preparation of one set of acoustic stimuli that can be used for all listeners and the models. The plausibility of this general approximation of HRTFs has been validated by Schwark et al. (2022). For both the left and right channel, reverberation time T30 had a maximum of 0.55 s at 0.25 kHz, and dropped towards higher frequencies up to 0.2 s at 8 kHz. Speech clarity C50 was larger at the left channel, which was closer to the wall behind the receiver. It varied between 9.9 dB at 0.125 kHz and 25.6 dB at 8 kHz for the left channel, and 5.1 dB at 0.25 kHz and 23.9 dB at 8 kHz for the right channel. Interaural cross-correlation IACC was highest at 0.125 kHz and had a second maximum at 1 kHz.

3.2. Measured speech recognition thresholds (SRTs)

To assess speech intelligibility in several conditions, SRTs were measured for different interferer constellations, with and without the presence of reverberation in a virtual living room. The results are presented in the following sections and are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15096923>.

3.2.1. Influence of interferer constellation

The influence of the interferer constellation in a (simulated) room on speech intelligibility was investigated. Fig. 2 shows SRTs in dB SNR at a level of 50 % correct words for different interferer constellations in anechoic (top left panel) and simulated reverberant (top right panel) conditions. To evaluate if the models are able to predict differences in speech intelligibility between different conditions, SRTs in dB SNR relative to the mean value are shown in anechoic (bottom left panel) and simulated reverberant (bottom right panel) conditions. The SRTs relative to the mean were calculated by subtracting the mean over five interferer constellations separately for each prediction model / measurement from the SRT values. The SNR is provided for the position at the receiver. Interferer constellations are displayed on the abscissa. The boxplots show the measured data of human listeners in terms of the median, the upper and lower quartiles, the maximum and minimum values within 1.5 times the interquartile range, and, if applicable, outlier data points. Predicted data for both models in different versions are indicated by single data points.

A two-way repeated measures ANOVA investigated the effects of the factors INTERFERER CONSTELLATION and REVERBERATION on the SRT. Mauchly's test indicated that sphericity had been met ($\chi^2(9) = 10.58$, $p = 0.31$ for factor INTERFERER CONSTELLATION; $\chi^2(9) = 9.15$, $p = 0.43$ for the interaction INTERFERER CONSTELLATION X REVERBERATION). The factors INTERFERER CONSTELLATION ($F(4,52) = 58.06$, $p < 0.001$), REVERBERATION ($F(1,13) = 5482.42$, $p < 0.001$), and the interaction INTERFERER CONSTELLATION X REVERBERATION ($F(4,52) = 57.61$, $p < 0.001$) were statistically significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

Due to the significant interaction of both factors, separate one-way repeated measures ANOVA were performed. One ANOVA investigated

Fig. 2. Measured and predicted speech recognition thresholds (SRTs) and SRTs relative to the mean comparing interferer constellations. Boxplots show the median, the upper and lower quartiles, the maximum and minimum values within 1.5 times the interquartile range and outlier data points of human listeners' measured data. Predicted data with FADE CAIN, FADE ABEL, BSIM EC on and BSIM EC off are shown additionally. Top left) SRTs in anechoic conditions, top right) SRTs in reverberant conditions, bottom left) SRTs relative to the mean in anechoic conditions, bottom right) SRTs relative to the mean in reverberant conditions. SRTs relative to the mean are calculated by subtracting the mean over 5 interferer constellations separately for each model / measurement from the SRT values. In the top panels, statistically significant differences between the data of human listeners are marked with *** for $p < 0.001$, ** for $0.001 \leq p < 0.01$, and * for $0.01 \leq p < 0.05$.

the anechoic data, and another ANOVA investigated the reverberant data. The effect of interferer constellation in anechoic conditions ($F(4,52) = 105.72, p < 0.001$) was statistically significant. The effect of interferer constellation in reverberant conditions ($F(4,52) = 9.25, p < 0.001$) was statistically significant as well. Results of post-hoc pairwise comparisons with a Bonferroni correction to adjust for multiple comparisons are marked with star symbols in Fig. 2 (top panels).

Interferer constellation significantly affected SRTs in the observed conditions. The effect was more pronounced in the anechoic conditions compared to reverberant conditions. In anechoic conditions, the lowest SRT of -19.5 dB SNR was obtained in the configuration with a large spatial separation of target and masker (*LR_anechoic*). The highest SRT of -15.4 dB SNR was obtained in the condition with target and noise coming from a similar direction (*K_anechoic*). Conditions with a combination of active noise sources resulted in intermediate SRTs of -17.3 dB SNR (*TV-D_anechoic*) and -18.5 dB SNR (*TV-LR-D_anechoic*). A similar value of

-18.2 dB SNR was obtained for the condition with a moderate level of spatial separation (*TV_anechoic*). The post-hoc pairwise comparisons in the anechoic conditions revealed the following statistically significant differences: The SRTs in *K_anechoic* were significantly higher than SRTs in all other interferer constellations (all comparisons with $p < 0.001$). SRTs in *LR_anechoic* were significantly lower than SRTs in *TV_anechoic*, *K_anechoic* and *TV-K_anechoic* ($p < 0.001$), and significantly lower than SRTs in *TV-LR-K_anechoic* ($p = 0.003$). Additionally, *TV-LR-K_anechoic* resulted in significantly lower SRTs than *TV_anechoic* ($p = 0.02$) and *TV-K_anechoic* ($p = 0.003$). This pattern is also supported by the SRTs relative to the mean in Fig. 2 (bottom left panel), where the deviations of the SRTs compared to the mean value are emphasized.

In reverberant conditions, the effect of spatial separation was reduced compared to anechoic conditions, resulting in a reduced effect size due to the reverberation. The lowest SRT of -9.8 dB SNR was found in the condition with noise coming from noise source K, which was the condition with the highest SRT (-15.4 dB SNR) in the anechoic situation.

The remaining interferer constellations resulted in slightly higher SRTs of up to -8.7 dB SNR (*TV-K_reverberant*). The post-hoc pairwise comparisons revealed the following significant differences between the interferer constellations in reverberant conditions: The SRTs in *K_reverberant* were significantly lower than SRTs in *TV_reverberant*, *TV-K_reverberant*, and *TV-LR-K_reverberant* ($p = 0.02$). In addition, the SRTs in *TV_reverberant* were significantly higher than in *LR_reverberant* ($p = 0.02$). The SRTs relative to the mean in the bottom right panel support these findings by showing only small differences of up to about 1 dB SNR across spatial conditions.

3.2.2. Influence of reverberation

The effect of reverberation on SRTs in different interferer constellations was also investigated. Fig. 3 shows the difference between the SRTs obtained under reverberant conditions and the SRTs obtained under anechoic conditions. The boxplots show the corresponding differences between reverberant and anechoic conditions for measured data. Predicted SRT differences for both models are indicated by single data points.

In all interferer constellations, reverberation caused an increase in SRT, i.e., there was a detrimental effect of reverberation on speech intelligibility performance. The largest detrimental effect of reverberation of 10.4 dB SNR was obtained in the condition *LR*, which was the condition with the largest spatial separation of speech and noise. The smallest detrimental effect of 6.2 dB SNR was found in the condition *K*, which had the smallest spatial separation of speech and noise. The remaining spatial conditions resulted in moderate effect sizes of reverberation: 9.1 dB SNR for *TV*, 8.9 dB SNR for *TV-K*, and 9.7 dB SNR for *TV-LR-K*.

Due to the significant interaction between the factors INTERFERER CONSTELLATION and REVERBERATION on SRT, paired samples *t*-tests with dependent samples were conducted to investigate the influence of reverberation for each interferer constellation. *T*-tests were conducted, because separate comparisons of the influence of reverberation in different interferer constellations were needed. Table A.1 (Appendix) provides an overview of two-sided *t*-test results. In each of the tested

interferer constellations, reverberation had a statistically significant detrimental effect on SRTs ($p < 0.001$). The results of the statistical analysis are also marked with star symbols in Fig. 3. The given *t*-values reflect the effect size in each interferer constellation.

3.3. Speech intelligibility predictions

In addition to SRT measurements with listeners, speech intelligibility in the same conditions was also predicted by models. In order to quantify the influence of binaural processing in complex acoustic conditions, the study investigated two versions for both FADE and BSIM: one with better ear listening only and another one with a combination of better ear listening and binaural processing. By this, the study investigated to what extent SRTs and SRTs relative to the mean could be predicted by the speech intelligibility models and to what extent the data can be explained by better ear listening. It was evaluated how accurate the impact of interferer constellation and presence of reverberation was predicted, and what influence binaural processing had in the models. The predicted SRTs are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15096923>.

SRTs and SRTs relative to the mean value predicted with each of the two versions of FADE and BSIM are shown in Fig. 2, additionally to measured data in boxplots. As for the measured data, the top panels show SRTs, and the bottom panels show the deviations of each SRT from the mean value across all conditions, providing a visual representation of the SRT relative to the mean per condition. The ability to predict the impact of reverberation on speech intelligibility performance is shown in Fig. 3, where the data quantifies the difference of SRTs between reverberant and anechoic conditions.

Fig. 4 shows an overview of all predicted SRTs in relation to the corresponding measured values. The bottom right boxes provide the results of bias, RMSE, and squared Pearson's correlation coefficient R^2 . These quantities were calculated for each model version. Considering all data, simulations with FADE tended to predict too low SRTs, reflected in

Fig. 3. Measured and predicted SRT differences of data in reverberant conditions with reference to anechoic data. Boxplots show the median, the upper and lower quartiles, the maximum and minimum values within 1.5 times the interquartile range and outlier data points of human listeners' measured data. Predicted data with FADE CAIN, FADE ABEL, BSIM EC on and BSIM EC off are shown additionally. Statistically significant differences between anechoic and reverberant data of human listeners are marked with *** for $p < 0.001$.

Fig. 4. Predicted SRTs in dB SNR as a function of measured SRTs in dB SNR at the receiver position for all conditions. Predicted SRTs are shown for the models FADE CAIN, FADE ABEL, BSIM EC on, and BSIM EC off. Please note that the predictions used pure-tone thresholds of 0 dB HL for all frequencies for simulations with all models. For FADE, in addition to the pure-tone thresholds a suprathreshold deficit of 1.9 dB was applied. The bottom right boxes denote the bias in dB, root-mean-square error (RMSE) in dB and squared Pearson correlation coefficient R^2 for each model version in relation to the measured results. The data cluster on the left side of the vertical line shows anechoic conditions, the cluster on the right side of the vertical line shows reverberant conditions.

negative bias values for both model versions. The RMSE was 3.2 dB for FADE *CAIN*, based on contralateral inhibition, and 2.8 dB for FADE *ABEL*, based on automatic better ear listening. Regarding bias and RMSE, the predictions obtained with FADE *ABEL* were slightly closer to the measured data. Both model versions showed high correlations with measured data, with $R^2 > 0.9$. The FADE *CAIN* version had a slightly higher correlation ($R^2 = 0.93$) than FADE *ABEL* ($R^2 = 0.91$). Simulations with BSIM showed smaller RMSE values for the version with *EC on* compared to *EC off* (bias of -1.0 dB and 1.2 dB; and RMSE of 2.1 dB and 3.2 dB, respectively). The correlation with BSIM *EC on* was comparable to the FADE predictions ($R^2 = 0.9$). Simulations with BSIM *EC off* showed a higher prediction error than BSIM *EC on*, with a lower correlation ($R^2 = 0.77$) and larger RMSE. This resulted from a large bias of BSIM *EC off* in anechoic conditions, although the effect of interferer constellation was predicted with a high correlation ($R^2 = 0.95$). In general, BSIM predictions tended to predict too high SRTs in the lower dB SNR range (i.e. anechoic conditions), and too low SRTs in the upper dB SNR range (i.e. reverberant conditions).

Additionally, Table 4 provides the results of the performance statistics separately for all data points, for anechoic data, and for reverberant data. These measures reveal that overall, the models performed better at predicting SRTs in anechoic conditions than in reverberant conditions. An exception to this trend is observed for BSIM *EC off*, where the bias and RMSE results yield better outcomes in the reverberant data conditions. The SRTs in different interferer constellations in anechoic conditions were predicted with a high R^2 , small RMSE and small bias by both FADE and BSIM, except for BSIM *EC off*. This is reflected by values of R^2 in the range of 0.90 (BSIM *EC on*) to 0.97 (FADE *ABEL* and FADE *CAIN*), RMSE in the range of 0.9 dB (FADE *ABEL*) to 1.9 dB (FADE *CAIN*), and bias in the range of -1.6 dB (FADE *CAIN*) to 0.7–0.8 dB (BSIM *EC on*; FADE *ABEL*), as shown in Table 4. Overall, the versions with better ear listening only (FADE *ABEL* and BSIM *EC off*) led to higher, i.e., worse SRTs than the corresponding versions with a combination of better ear listening and binaural processing (FADE *CAIN* and BSIM *EC on*), particularly in anechoic conditions. These differences were found to be less pronounced in reverberant conditions. In reverberant conditions, the predictions mostly predicted too low (too good) SRTs and underestimated the impact of reverberation. This phenomenon is also shown in Fig. 3, where the detrimental effect of reverberation was less pronounced in the simulations than in the measured data. It should be stressed that for measured SRTs, there were hardly differences between the interferer constellations in reverberant cases, so there was almost no variation to be predicted by the models. This was also reflected by very low correlations between measured and predicted data in reverberant conditions, ranging from $R^2 = 0.03$ (FADE *CAIN*) to $R^2 = 0.33$ (FADE *ABEL*).

Table A.2 (Appendix) provides results of a *t*-test comparing the

Table 4

Measures comparing the measured and predicted data for all conditions, and separately for anechoic and reverberant conditions, for the model versions FADE *ABEL*, FADE *CAIN*, BSIM *EC off*, and BSIM *EC on*. Shown are the bias in dB, root-mean-square error (RMSE) in dB and squared Pearson correlation coefficient R^2 . Values in bold indicate $p < 0.05$.

Data	Model	Bias / dB	RMSE / dB	R^2	p
All	FADE <i>ABEL</i>	-1.5	2.8	0.91	< 0.001
	FADE <i>CAIN</i>	-2.9	3.2	0.93	< 0.001
	BSIM <i>EC off</i>	1.2	3.2	0.77	< 0.001
	BSIM <i>EC on</i>	-1.0	2.1	0.90	< 0.001
Anechoic	FADE <i>ABEL</i>	0.8	0.9	0.97	0.002
	FADE <i>CAIN</i>	-1.6	1.9	0.97	0.003
	BSIM <i>EC off</i>	4.1	4.1	0.95	0.005
	BSIM <i>EC on</i>	0.7	1.0	0.90	0.014
Reverberant	FADE <i>ABEL</i>	-3.8	3.8	0.33	0.312
	FADE <i>CAIN</i>	-4.1	4.1	0.03	0.573
	BSIM <i>EC off</i>	-1.8	1.9	0.13	0.545
	BSIM <i>EC on</i>	-2.6	2.7	0.29	0.349

correlation values R^2 between the different models (introduced above), and the 2-tailed *p*-value was reported to show whether the difference between the compared models is significant. This test showed that when considering all data, BSIM *EC off* correlated significantly worse with the data of human listeners than the other models: FADE *CAIN* ($t = 3.843$, $p = 0.006$), FADE *ABEL* ($t = 3.183$, $p = 0.015$), BSIM *EC on* ($t = 2.622$, $p = 0.034$). The remaining model comparisons with regard to the correlation with human listener data did not yield significantly different performances.

3.4. Role of binaural processing in simulations

The prediction models FADE and BSIM were both applied in versions with better ear listening only and with a combination of better ear listening and binaural processing. This section examines the influence of binaural processing in the conducted speech intelligibility performance predictions in anechoic and reverberant conditions.

In FADE predictions, the use of *CAIN* led to lower, i.e., better SRT values than the use of *ABEL* (see Fig. 2). The difference between both model versions was approximately 2–3 dB for anechoic conditions, and <1 dB for reverberant conditions. The role of binaural processing was therefore especially crucial in anechoic conditions. As shown in Table 4, in anechoic conditions, FADE *CAIN* predicted slightly too low SRTs (bias = -1.6 dB), while FADE *ABEL* predicted slightly too high SRTs (bias = 0.8 dB). In reverberant conditions, both versions predicted too low SRTs, with FADE *ABEL* being slightly closer to the measured values (bias = -3.8 dB) as compared to FADE *CAIN* (bias = -4.1 dB). The overall correlation between measured and predicted SRTs was high for both model versions, with $R^2 = 0.93$ and $R^2 = 0.91$ for FADE *CAIN* and *ABEL*, respectively.

In BSIM predictions, a similar behavior was observed. Again, the SRTs were lower for the version *EC on* compared to *EC off*. In this case, the effect of binaural processing was more pronounced compared to FADE predictions. The difference between BSIM predictions with and without the EC stage was in a range of approximately 3–4 dB for anechoic conditions, and up to approximately 1 dB for reverberant conditions. BSIM *EC on* resulted in SRTs close to the measured values in anechoic conditions (bias = 0.7 dB), while BSIM *EC off* resulted in substantially higher SRTs (bias = 4.1 dB). In reverberant conditions, both model versions led to an overestimation of SRTs – the predicted SRTs were lower than the measured data (bias = -1.8 dB for BSIM *EC off*; bias = -2.6 dB for BSIM *EC on*).

4. Discussion

This study evaluated the performance of speech intelligibility predictions with the model FADE in complex acoustic environments, examining the influence of interferer constellations in a simulated room with and without reverberation. As mentioned in the introduction, research on the performance in rooms of ASR-based speech intelligibility prediction models like FADE is still very limited. This study advances this validation by combining a room model with a speech intelligibility model and validating the predictions based on measured normal-hearing listener data and the reference model BSIM. The use of a room model enabled an independent observation of different combinations of interferer constellations and the presence of reverberation. These spatial conditions were based on setups of a realistic living room and acoustic measurements in the present physical version of this room. To evaluate the impact of binaural processing on the tested binaural conditions, both speech intelligibility models FADE and BSIM were tested with better ear listening only and a combination of better ear listening and binaural processing. It was found that FADE in both versions leads to a similar prediction accuracy as BSIM in the version with better ear listening and binaural processing. The evaluated speech intelligibility models were able to predict the effect of interferer constellation in anechoic cases with a high accuracy, and showed limits in predicting speech

intelligibility in simulated reverberant conditions, represented here by a living room.

4.1. Speech recognition threshold predictions with FADE and BSIM

The current study evaluates both FADE and BSIM in predicting speech recognition thresholds, i.e., the speech SNR required to obtain a fixed speech intelligibility (here: average rate of 50 % words correctly recognized in a sentence). FADE, as a reference-free model, provides absolute predictions of speech intelligibility, which are highly accurate in anechoic conditions ($R^2 = 0.97$), and comparable to the prediction accuracy with BSIM *EC on*. In contrast to FADE, BSIM, as a reference-based model, provides relative predictions that are calibrated to the mean SRT of normal-hearing listeners. A reference-free model like FADE therefore offers the advantage that no empirical data are required for the specific condition to be evaluated. Evaluating model predictions under anechoic conditions provides a controlled basis for isolating and critically assessing the contributions of individual binaural processing stages as well as their relative importance for predictions under reverberant conditions.

As expected, FADE *CAIN* predicted the SRTs with a slight negative prediction bias compared to the listeners. In general, FADE corresponds rather to the best-performing listeners and tends to predict lower SRTs than in the listening experiment. This behavior is expected, because FADE knows the test material components from the training (i.e., FADE uses a matched training approach) and therefore behaves as a generalized optimum detector (Holube and Kollmeier, 1996; Jürgens and Brand, 2009). This bias was less apparent in predictions with BSIM. BSIM uses a reference condition and is calibrated to the mean SRT of normal-hearing listeners, whereas FADE does not. Therefore, based on the model implementation, FADE predicts the intelligibility performance of the optimal/best performer, whereas BSIM predicts that of the average performer.

In terms of normalized data, where only the relative differences between conditions are evaluated (see Fig. 2), the performance of both models was comparable.

BSIM is already a well-established binaural speech intelligibility model, evaluated by a wide range of studies (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006; Beutelmann et al., 2010; Huelsmeier et al., 2021; Rennie et al., 2011, 2014). Huelsmeier et al., 2021 showed a comparable accuracy of BSIM and FADE *CAIN* for predictions in spatial listening conditions limited to one noise source. The current results extend this and demonstrate that both models perform similarly in a more complex condition with multiple noise sources. The next step could involve an evaluation of the model's accuracy for individual speech intelligibility in both unaided and aided conditions, considering spatially more complex environments like the one presented in this study.

4.2. Influence of binaural processing

FADE *CAIN* and BSIM *EC on* apply a different approach of binaural processing. FADE *CAIN* is based on binaural processing using contralateral inhibition acting on the feature stage of the model, while BSIM uses the EC algorithm acting on the signal stage of the model and making use of interaural level and time differences. Nevertheless, they lead to similar results in the observed spatial conditions, and both models show similar correlations with human listener data.

It was investigated to what extent the binaural processing in speech intelligibility models had an effect on the predicted SRTs. The expectation from literature (Schädler et al., 2020b) was that FADE *CAIN* yields more accurate predictions than FADE *ABEL* in the conditions where interferers are on only one side of the head, because in FADE *CAIN*, binaural information is added on the feature stage. In the here considered spatial conditions, lower SRTs were achieved using FADE *CAIN*, which fits the expectation. A comparable behavior was observed for BSIM, i.e. the simulated SRTs are lower for the combination of better-ear

listening and binaural processing than when only better-ear listening (*EC off*) is considered.

As expected, the largest differences between FADE *CAIN* and FADE *ABEL* or between BSIM *EC on* and BSIM *EC off* were present in anechoic asymmetric setups with the largest spatial distance between target and noise sources (*LR_anechoic*). In nearly co-located conditions (*K_anechoic*), the effect of binaural processing was observed to be smaller, while the importance of the additional binaural processing component is more present in conditions with a larger spatial separation of target and noise sources. The model versions can describe the binaural advantage to a different amount. For both FADE and BSIM, the difference between the better ear approach only and the better ear approach with binaural processing stage is smaller in reverberant conditions than in anechoic conditions. For FADE, both model versions hardly differ in reverberant conditions, and for BSIM, no differences are observed for symmetric conditions and small differences are observed for asymmetric reverberant conditions. Reverberation causes a decorrelation across both ears in the late reflections, which can degrade source separation (Kendall, 1995) and could explain these findings. Even the comparatively short reverberation time, as here in the living room, influences the binaural cues so strongly that the advantage of spatial separation of speech and noise for speech intelligibility is marginal.

4.3. Influence of reverberation

Both prediction models showed limitations in reverberant conditions by underestimating the SRT in these conditions, and underestimating the relative effect of reverberation compared to anechoic conditions as opposed to the listener data. For predictions with FADE compared to measured performance with human listeners in reverberant conditions, the negative prediction bias towards too low SRTs could be caused by the model learning the reverberation in the training phase (so-called matched training). In the testing phase, the model can use these trained cues depending on the reverberation of each condition and therefore show a negative prediction bias. In contrast to human listeners, the presence of reverberation seems to affect the predicted speech intelligibility performance to a smaller amount, because it is known by the model. The BSIM model, which uses the SII, is primarily based on the SNR at the ears and therefore does not explicitly model all effects of reverberation. BSIM accounts for the decorrelation of binaural information due to reverberation, which reduces the binaural masking release. Moreover, reverberation causes interfering noise to arrive from multiple directions, effectively reducing the SNR advantage at the better ear by spatially diffusing the noise. This means that reverberation impacts not only binaural processing but also the better-ear effect. This better-ear effect is modeled by comparing the band-specific SNRs at both ears and selecting the higher value. In contrast to both of these detrimental effects on binaural processing, the SII is not sensitive to the detrimental effect of reverberation on speech intelligibility. Therefore, under realistic reverberant conditions, the model may underpredict speech recognition thresholds due to this limitation.

In agreement with the findings of the present study, previous studies have shown that BSIM does not always produce satisfactory results under reverberant conditions for certain listening scenarios (Beutelmann et al., 2010; Rennie et al., 2011). Rennie et al. (2011) have shown that this reduced precision is more severe in highly reverberant conditions compared to conditions with less reverberation. They also found an underprediction of SRTs by BSIM in reverberant conditions. These findings hold for conditions in which the target is far away from the listener, so that not only the noise but also the target is affected by the reverberation. There is another BSIM model version where the room impulse response of the target is split into a useful early reflection part and a detrimental late reverberation part (Rennie et al., 2011). This was shown to lead to an improved prediction performance in reverberant conditions compared to the standard BSIM configuration, particularly for large listener-to-speaker distances beyond the critical

distance (Minelli et al., 2023). Please note, that in all spatial conditions of the present study, the listener was within the range where direct sound dominated, as the distance between target and listener was below the critical distance. Therefore, reverberation can be assumed to have a negligible influence on the target signal. Another study reporting an underprediction of the effect of reverberation by BSIM was published by Beutelmann et al. (2010). There was a negative prediction bias throughout all levels of reverberation, meaning that predicted SRTs were below measured SRTs in all conditions. This magnitude of this negative bias increased for reverberant rooms compared to the anechoic condition, showing the underprediction of the reverberation impact compared to the measured data, which is similar to the present study.

The effect of reverberation on the listeners of this study was considerably higher than in literature (Biberger and Ewert, 2019; Neuman et al., 2010), which contributes further to the difference between predictions and measurements in these conditions. This observation could be caused by the artificial type of reverberation generated by the room model, resulting in elevated SRTs of the listeners. The generation of an acoustically precise reverberation was out of scope of the present study, so there were some limitations in the design of the room model. The sound sources were omnidirectional as opposed to natural sources which include directivity patterns, and the image source model for early reflections only applied reflections of first order. It is likely that the early reflections did not contain as much energy as the late reflections because the image sources were only simulated up to the first order. Late reverberation was rendered independently from the early reflections. While early reflections are considered useful for speech intelligibility, late reverberation is considered detrimental. If the reverberant signals contain a disproportionate amount of late reverberation compared to early reflections, this could lead to higher than expected SRTs in reverberant conditions. Thus, human listening data in reverberant conditions is shifted up, whereas predictions may be able to exploit the entire reverberant tail, resulting in down-shifted SRTs. This results in a large offset between measurements and predictions in the reverberant conditions tested.

Furthermore, the binaural synthesis of signals was performed statically and with generic HRTFs, which is only an approximation and does not represent completely the perception of listening to real sources in a sound field. The large effect of reverberation in measurements and the resulting underprediction of the reverberation effect by the speech intelligibility models could be caused by this approximation and maybe be reduced by exchanging the static generic HRTFs by dynamic individual HRTFs.

4.4. Perspectives and outlook

The results presented here provide a validation of FADE for use in spatial room conditions that reflect real-life listening scenarios. In case of reverberation, it was learned that the FADE prediction results should be treated with caution, but the quantitative evaluation of the prediction bias provides valuable information for the interpretation of future simulations, as it could be seen as a calibration offset when interpreting predicted SRTs in reverberation. To reduce this negative prediction bias, a possible model extension could be the use of randomized reverberation within the training phase, or no reverberation at all in the training. This could prevent the model from learning reverberant, condition-specific cues and thus reduce the performance, more closely matching the results of human listeners in reverberation. Furthermore, similar measurements as the presented ones could be conducted using a refined room simulation or using real room recordings to cancel out possible effects of artificial reverberation.

The FADE predictions in anechoic spatial conditions showed a high precision, except for a bias towards best-performing listeners. This raises the perspective of using FADE for model-based SRT assessments in environments that are one step more realistic than typical clinical tests. One may use FADE to create a pre-selection of relevant spatial

configurations, as the spatial effect of the binaural difference was predicted with a high precision. Thus, in order to determine which conditions in an SRT measurement would be of interest to analyze and where relevant differences can be expected, one can first run FADE predictions. In the future, it will also be of interest to validate FADE in spatial conditions for individual listeners with hearing loss, and to test whether FADE can predict individual differences in complex conditions. Schädler et al. (2020a) have shown that FADE can account for individual performance predictions in monaural conditions, which raises the question if this is also possible in complex conditions.

5. Conclusions

The most important findings of this study are the following:

1. It was shown that a new approach of speech intelligibility predictions can be validated by combining models of speech recognition with binaural signals rendered by a room simulation toolbox.
2. The reference-free model FADE led to a small negative prediction bias, especially with the binaural version CAIN, which did not occur for the reference-based model BSIM *EC on*. The prediction accuracy in terms of the coefficient of determination R^2 was higher for FADE than for BSIM, with $R^2 = [0.91, 0.93]$ for FADE *ABEL* and FADE *CAIN*, compared to $R^2 = [0.77, 0.90]$ for BSIM *EC off* and BSIM *EC on*, respectively. So, it was shown that FADE as an ab-initio, reference-free model can produce predictions of high accuracy in spatial conditions of different complexity.
3. The difference in SRTs between FADE *CAIN* and FADE *ABEL* could be interpreted as a measure for the advantage of binaural processing. It was shown that the contribution of binaural processing in FADE based on the contralateral inhibition is quantitatively comparable to that of BSIM based on EC processing.
4. More research appears necessary to improve the speech intelligibility prediction accuracy in reverberation. The observed differences between FADE predictions and measured data in simulated reverberant conditions are most likely caused by FADE's access to the reverberation pattern in the matched training of the model, and artifacts due to the artificial type of reverberation.

Data availability statement

Research data for this article is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15096923>. The repository contains the simulated BRIRs, rendered noise signals, and measured and predicted SRTs.

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Merle Gerken: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christopher F. Hauth:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Birger Kollmeier:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.heares.2025.109400](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2025.109400).

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